

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and the Ghost Neutrino

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of the 8T, of coupling constants under the first representation of net curvature, and adding to the electron an additional term, which has no curvature converging inward, i.e. no mass, it is possible to add the neutrino to each term of the coupling constants series. The electron neutrino is part of the EMT symmetry and is represented by a symmetry operator which is unbroken, explaining the massless trait and keeping the primordial term preserved as it is concerning measured magnitude.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. From experiment, we know that the electron does not propagate by itself but rather with another ghost particle, the electron neutrino. What kind of numerical traits in the 8T this particle possess? In other words, we need to add it the coupling term (1.44) without changing the magnitude of the coupling. If reader is familiar with the 8T two symmetry breaking – inward to generate mass:

$$8 - (1)$$

Moreover, outward to generate a ripple on the matric tensor given by the term:

$$8 + (1)$$

The answer is clear the ghost particle, the electron neutrino cannot be associated with neither symmetry breaking classes. It has the be a particle which has no effect on the coupling term, we can represent it but it will vanish. The answer than is that the electron neutrino is represented by the following numerical trait that associate with vanishing in the 8T:

$$v_e \rightarrow 8n ;$$

$$n \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + 8 + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + v_e + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.47)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + v_e + (e)] + \gamma = 128 \quad (1.48)$$

$$v_e = 0$$

$$[(24 * 5) + \nu_e + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \quad (1.49)$$

Based on the 8T we can predict that the electron neutrino will be massless, in order for the coupling term to stay as it is. The same apply to each higher generation neutrino according to the EMT symmetry. The fact it has no mass does not mean it cannot exert pressure. The photon is massless, it can exert pressure. If the photon will propagate on a tiny mass measuring scale it will cause the measuring scale to differ from zero due to the pressure it exerts, and effective mass as it is raw energy. Summing up, it is possible to represent the electron neutrino by using a perfect symmetry multiplier that does not affect the coupling term. The fact it is a perfect symmetry multiplier means the electron neutrino has no mass. That is in agreement with experiment.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)